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Operational Skills Possessed by Office Management and Technology (OMT) Lecturers' for Effective Course Content Delivery in Rivers State Universities

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the operational skills possessed by Office Management and Technology (OMT) Lecturers for effective course content delivery in Rivers State Universities. Three specific objectives; three research questions and five hypotheses guided the study. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of 42 respondents. The entire population was used for the study since the population size was manageable. Two structured questionnaires titled "Questionnaire on Operational Skills Possessed by Office Management and Technology Lecturers for Effective Course Content Delivery (SPOMTLEEC)" and questionnaire on effective course content delivery in Universities (QECDU)" were used to obtain data for the study. The instruments were validated by three experts (Two in Business Education and one in measurement and evaluation). The reliability of the instruments was obtained through test-retest method and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients of 0.89 and 0.84 were obtained respectively. The research questions were answered with Pearson Product Moment Correlation while the hypotheses were tested with t-transformation at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study showed that; Microsoft Access skills, Microsoft Excel skills and Graphic design skills of OMT Lecturers in Rivers State Universities enhance effective course content delivery. Based on the findings, it was recommended that, Microsoft Access skills, Microsoft Excel skills, and Graphic design skills should be properly incorporated into OMT programme to enhance effective course content delivery by OMT lecturers.

Keywords: operational skills, Office Management, lecturers

INTRODUCTION

Office Management and Technology (OMT) course in Nigeria has been evolving with the advancement in office work and technology. As a response, many tertiary institutions in Nigeria have now changed the nomenclature from secretarial education / studies to Office Management and Technology (OMT) or OTM in some schools. Igbinedion (2019) stated that secretarial education which gave birth to Office Management and Technology started in the United States of America in the 17th and 18th centuries. By the 19th and 20th centuries the course expanded rapidly to some developed and developing countries. Igbinedion also explained that OMT course is a specialized phase of vocational education that prepares students to enter teaching and office occupations as capable and intelligent members of the office force. Adebayo (2021) opined that the OMT programme was planned for two major reasons, first, it is as a response to the yearnings of the Secretarial Studies students and practitioners on the need to change the name of the programme as they are only relevant at the traditional office environment. Secondly, and most importantly, as a result of the change in curriculum with more emphasis on Information and

Communication Technology (ICT) and a change of name to match the current trend would enrich the knowledge of the students and equip them with necessary skills needed in today's office environment.

The above reasons agreed with the aims of OMT programme as stipulated by the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) (2014), which is to produce graduates who should fit properly into the offices of computerized organizations and perform professionally in their areas. Office Management and Technology Education has always been dedicated to preparing its graduates for the world of work. This can be achieved if the students are put through the relevant components of the OMT programme, especially operational skills which according to Nwana (2020), include office application, office technology, business and administrative management, numeric component, general studies and Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES).

Akinyele (2015) opined that students learn job specifics and employability skills and are given opportunities to use these skills through work experience programmes that connect them with the work environment. Akinyele further asserted that to be effective in preparing students for a changing workplace and society, Office Management and Technology (OMT) must extend beyond the delivery of theory but also the required skills and work experience. The objectives, theoretical and practical contents of the new curriculum are geared towards integrating graduates of OMT Departments into the evolution of technology (Atuenyi, 2011). This OMT curriculum was designed in a way that the teaching and learning of Office Application which consists of ICT office application I, ICT office application II, desktop publishing, webpage design and management information system were included.

Rapid advancement in ICT has made it possible for people in different parts of the world to communicate face-to-face through satellite, video conferencing as well as transmit faxes embodying complex designs drawings via regular telephone lines. Lecturers have to be prepared to confront the challenges of the emerging technologies in order to fit into the industrial and information society of this global era. The rapid advancement in technology and new innovations have created various business needs, wants, challenges and has opened new opportunities like e-business, e-communication, e-purchasing, e-marketing, e-finance, e-learning and e-service. All these make the use of electronic devices to conduct business practices on-line. These new opportunities pose enormous challenges to OMT lecturers and society at large. There is an urgent need to ensure that those coming through education and those currently in the workforce have the right skills for this evolving sector. There is no doubt that a comparative advantage of any nation is a function of the capacity of her population to embrace new technologies and incorporate them into production process (Okoro, 2013). Secretaries as integral part of the organizations in any nation are also influenced by innovations and modern ways of doing things due to the introduction of technology. The role of the secretary has been affected with the invasion of sophistication and dynamism in office activities as secretaries now work on computer terminals that are connected to networks like the internet (Akpomi, Chiorluu & Nwanewezi, 2015).

Etonyeaku (2010) observed that the new trends in the office are office information systems and these new trends in technological innovation place greater responsibilities on OMT lecturers and secretarial studies students. Expertise with the current applications is very crucial to business educators' effectiveness in the teaching and learning of the new curriculum. The advantages of the knowledge of the packages to the students are not far-fetched. This is buttressed by the stance of Ohakwe and Okwuanaso in Akiti and Onyema (2010) that the knowledge of computer application software such as Spreadsheet, Excel, Computer Aided Design and Data-Base management are important skills that should be imparted on the recipients of business education. This will enable them to compete favorably in the business world and fit in well in the ICT oriented offices.

This implies that it is necessary to determine the level of operational skills possessed by OMT lecturers in the teaching of office application. Level in this context is defined as the competency stage attained by the lecturers in the utilization of operational skills involved in teaching office applications. The OMT Lecturers play prominent role in preparing students, and are expected to demonstrate professional qualities. If the business education/studies teachers should demonstrate professional qualities, it is imperative that they must, according to Omeje (2016) not only have the deep rooted knowledge and competencies in the ICT equipment and operations of automotive office facilities such as

microcomputers, networking facilities, internet facilities, reprographics, duplicating and micrographic machines but must effectively teach skills in these areas to students.

Operational skills refer to those areas in the course that pertain to the mode of doing by following the procedures involved. It is those skills in the component areas of office application which the teacher shows to the students by way of demonstration. It is, therefore, doubtful whether the teachers have been trained to effectively handle the course. The lecturers may have the teaching abilities but they cannot teach office application without operational skills. Ezenwafor and Okeke (2015) identified low level of skills as a key factor that inhibit learning in ICT environment. Students do not perform well in their work places because they do not possess the information processing skills demanded of them. This affects the aims of National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) stated above.

Omeje (2016) stressed that business education teachers should acquire modern ICT competencies so as to effectively impart these skills to the students. Students also should be adequately prepared to meet up with the demands of the present day technological innovations in business and offices. Recently, the issues of how and why teachers themselves should be highly skilled in the use of ICT in teaching and learning have dominated most seminars and conferences in order not to produce half-baked graduates that will not be able to get job or contribute meaningfully to national development (Omeje, 2016).

Teaching of office applications in the Universities in Eastern Nigeria require operational skills such as Microsoft Access skills, Microsoft Excel skills, graphic design skills, Spreadsheet skills, and Database Management skills. Possession of these skills will ensure that the graduates of the programme develop relevant and saleable competencies that would enable the graduates to be self-employed and also to create employment after graduation.

Microsoft access is a form of Database Management System (DBMS) designed by Microsoft Corporation to facilitate data independence, share ability, consistency and non-redundancy (Ayatalumo, Ezeano, Ezeano, Ezeorah & Ugboaja, 2014). They further defined a data base as a collection of data items stored with a minimum of duplication so as to provide a consistent and controlled pool of operational data. It is simply information related to a particular subject or purposes such as tracking customer orders. Vikas in Nnorom (2019) described Microsoft excel as one of the most versatile and popular spreadsheet programs. It serves as well as complex mathematical operations. Excel also provides the facility to convert the spreadsheet data into various charts like bar, pie, 2D, and 3D. When converted into charts, the spreadsheet data can easily be understood.

Graphic design is the art and practice of planning and projecting ideas and experiences with visual and textual content (Cezzar, 2015). Graphic design focuses on developing skills in the following areas: drawing and illustration, poster designing and greeting cards, lettering, sign writing and calligraphy, layout, designing and construction of articles with paper, print-making, packaging designing, book craft, creating images and designing visual communication items in the computer.

Desktop publishing is the process of using computer and desktop publisher to combine texts and graphics to produce documents such as newsletters, brochures, posters and books (Azuka, 2012). Desktop publishing is used to design materials for publication. It helps for easy management of textbooks and magazines and preparation of calendars, invitation cards, posters and identity cards among others. Students are expected to be highly skilled in the use of the application for different purposes. Okoro and Ndinechi (2013) stated that desktop publishing skills include the ability to open desktop environment, identify and use documents, produce a simple, publications, set up page size / orientation and margins of a flier and create quality and attractive text area / text frame.

A database management system (DBMS) is an application used for creating and managing databases. It provides users and programmers a systematic way to create, store, retrieve, update and manage data and makes it possible for end users to create, read, update and delete data in a database, DBMS essentially serves as an interface between the database and end users or application programmes, ensuring that data are consistently organized and remain easily accessible. It manages the data, the database engine that allows data to be accessed, locked and modified, and the database schema, which defines the database's logical structure. These three foundational elements help provide concurrency, security, data integrity and uniform administration procedures. The DBMS is perhaps most useful for providing a centralized view of

data that can be accessed by multiple users, from multiple locations in a controlled manner. It can limit what data the end user sees as well as how that end user can view the data, providing many views of a single database schema. End users and software programmers are free from having to understand where the data are physically located or the type of storage media the data resides on because the DBMS handles all requests.

There are different kinds of database according to how they are organized. A hierarchical database organizes its contents in a hierarchical mode; identifies the data element and defines the relationship among these data elements. A relational model organizes data elements in a two-dimensional table consisting of rows and columns. Each row contains information belonging to one entry in the database. Data within a row is a data recorded and each column is a data field. Students are expected to understand the database environment, be able to load and quit database management system, use the tool bars and apply the menu commands, exhibit competence on how to open a database table, setting of field properties, creating, modifying tables, input data and records into a database, save and print.

Statement of the Problem

The introduction of ICT as part of OMT curriculum in universities by the National Universities Commission in 2015 has influenced how lecturers teach university students. This is based on the fact that new ICT packages like Microsoft excel and Microsoft access, web design among others were introduced into the curriculum. The reason for introducing it was to improve the ability of OMT lecturers in teaching OMT courses then contribute to the growth, development and advancement of OMT courses and enhance the ability of OMT graduates to function maximally in the workplace due to the changing nature of today's work life and workplace.

However, it has been observed that most resource persons (lecturers) in office management and technology still teach OMT courses the old way as against the new way where OMT students are taught in practical terms because these resource persons do not possess these operational skills that are needed to enhance course content delivery. It is on this premise that this study seeks to ascertain the operational skill that are possessed by OMT lecturers for effective course content delivery in Rivers State Universities.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the operational skills possessed by Office Management and Technology (OMT) Lecturers for Effective Course Content Delivery in Rivers State Universities. Specifically, the study sought to;

8. Ascertain the level of relationship that exist between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Access skill and effective course content delivery in Rivers State Universities.
9. Ascertain the level of relationship that exist between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Excel skill and effective course content delivery in Rivers State Universities.
10. Ascertain the level of relationship that exist between OMT lecturers' Graphic Design skill and effective course content delivery in Rivers State Universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study;

1. What level of relationship exist between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Access skill and effective course content delivery in Universities in Rivers State?
2. What level of relationship exist between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Excel skill and effective course content delivery in Rivers State Universities?
3. What level of relationship exist between OMT lecturers' Graphic Design skill and effective course content delivery in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. There is no significant relationship between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Access skill and effective course content delivery in in Rivers State Universities.
2. There is no significant relationship between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Excel skill and effective course content delivery in Rivers State Universities.

3. There is no significant relationship between OMT lecturers' Graphic Design skill and effective course content delivery in Rivers State Universities.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational research design to establish the relationship between the variables. The study was conducted in Rivers State. Rivers State is in the South – South geopolitical zone of Nigeria and one of the thirty-six states in the country. The population of the study comprised 42 Lecturers in Business Education Department in the two state-owned universities (Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education), both in Port Harcourt. The entire population was used for the study. Hence, there was no sampling. The two instruments for data collection were self-structured questionnaires. The first one is titled “Operational Skills Possessed by OMT Lecturers for Effective Course Content Delivery in Universities in Rivers State (OSOLECCD). This questionnaire is divided into two sections (Section A and Section B). Section A is on the demographic data while section B is for the response options and items. The response options of the questionnaire are on a 4-point rating scale of High Level (HL), Moderate Level (ML), Low Level (LL), Very Low Level (VLL). The second instrument on effective content delivery was structured on a 4-point rating scale of High Level (HL), Moderate Level (ML), Low Level (LL), and Very Low Level (VLL).

The instruments were subjected to face and content validation to determine their adequacy and appropriateness for the study. This was done by presenting the instrument, statement of problem, purpose of the study, research questions and hypotheses to three experts, two Business Educators and one in Measurement and Evaluation. Based on their comments and suggestions the instruments were modified to suit the study.

Test-retest method was used to establish the reliability of the instruments with Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients. The reliability coefficient obtained from the first instrument was 0.89 and the reliability coefficient obtained from the second instrument was 0.84. The instrument for the study were administered to the respondents with the help of two assistants who were instructed by the Researcher on what to do. Data were analyzed with Pearson Product Moment Correlation while t-transformation was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Research question 1: *What level of relationship exist between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Access skills and effective content delivery in Universities in Rivers State?*

Table 4.1: Relationship between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Access skills and Effective Content Delivery in Rivers State Universities

Variables	Σx Σy	Σx^2 Σy^2	Σxy	r-cal	Level of Relationship
Microsoft Access Skill	19.09	60.14	41.9	0.75	Strong Level
Effective Content Delivery	21.57	46.68			

Source: Field Survey 2025

From the analysis in table 4.1, $\Sigma x = 19.09$, $\Sigma y = 21.57$, the summation of x^2 and y^2 were thus 60.14 and 46.68, Σxy 41.9 and the r-calculated is 0.75. The value of the r-calculated (r-cal) indicates that there is a strong level of relationship between lecturers' Microsoft Access Skill and effective content delivery.

Research Question 2: *What level of relationship exist between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Excel skills and effective content delivery in Universities in Rivers State?*

Table 4.2: Relationship between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Excel skills and Effective Content Delivery in Rivers State Universities

Variables	Σx Σy	Σx^2 Σy^2	Σxy	r-cal	Level of Relationship
Microsoft Excel Skill	14.94	54.4			
Effective Content Delivery	21.57	46.68	39.6	0.76	Strong Level

Source: Field Survey 2025

From the analysis in table 4.2, $\Sigma x = 14.94$, $\Sigma y = 21.57$, the summation of x^2 and y^2 are thus 54.4 and 46.68, Σxy 39.6 respectively and the r-calculated (r-cal) is 0.76. The value of the r-calculated shows that there is a strong level of relationship between lecturers' Microsoft Excel Skill and effective content delivery.

Research Question 3: *What level of relationship exist between OMT lecturers' Graphic Design skills and effective content delivery in Universities in Rivers State?*

Table 4.3: Relationship between OMT lecturers' Graphic Design skills and Effective Content Delivery in Rivers State Universities

Variables	Σx Σy	Σx^2 Σy^2	Σxy	r-cal	Level of Relationship
Graphic Design Skill	18.23	55.4			
Effective Content Delivery	21.57	46.68	40.07	0.74	Strong Level

Source: Field Survey 2025

From the analysis in table 4.3 indicates that values of Σx and Σy are 18.23 and 21.57, Σx^2 and Σy^2 are 55.4 and 46.68 respectively, Σxy is 40.07 and the r-calculated value is 0.74. The r-calculated value indicates that there is a strong level of relationship between lecturers' Graphic Design Skill and effective content delivery.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship Between OMT Lecturers' Microsoft Access skill and Effective Content Delivery in Universities in Rivers State.

Table 6: T-transformation of Relationship between OMT Lecturers' Microsoft Access Skill and Effective Content Delivery

Variables	Σx Σy	Σx^2 Σy^2	Σxy	t-trans.	t-crit	df	Level of sign	Decision
Microsoft Access Skill	19.09	60.14					0.05	
Effective Content Delivery	21.57	46.68	41.9	0.75	1.984	40		Significant

Source: Field Survey 2025

The analysis in table 4.6 shows that the value for the t-transformation (t-trans.) is 6.9 while the value of the t-critical (t-crit) is 1.984 at 0.05 level of significance. The value of the t-trans. is higher than the value of the t-crit. Therefore, there is significant relationship between OMT Lecturers' Microsoft Access Skill and Effective Content Delivery in Universities in Rivers State.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant relationship Between OMT Lecturers' Microsoft Excel skill and Effective Content Delivery in Universities in Rivers State.

Table 4.7: T-transformation of Relationship between OMT Lecturers' Microsoft Excel Skill and Effective Content Delivery

Variables	Σx Σy	Σx^2 Σy^2	Σxy	t-trans.	t-crit	df	Level of sign	Decision
Microsoft Access Skill	14.94	54.4	39.6	7.2	1.984	40	0.05	Significant
Effective Content Delivery	21.57	46.68						

Source: Field Survey 2025

The analysis in table 4.7 shows that the value for the t-transformation (t-trans.) is 7.2 while the value of the t-critical (t-crit) is 1.984. The value of the t-trans. is higher than the value of the t-crit. Therefore, there is significant relationship between OMT Lecturers' Microsoft Excel Skill and Effective Content Delivery in Universities in Rivers State.

Hypotheses 3: There is no significant relationship between OMT Lecturers' Graphic Design skill and Effective Content Delivery in Universities in Rivers State.

Table 4.8: T-transformation of Relationship between OMT Lecturers' Graphic Design Skill and Effective Content Delivery

Variables	Σx Σy	Σx^2 Σy^2	Σxy	t-trans.	t-crit	df	Level of sign	Decision
Graphic Design Skill	18.23	53.4	40.07	6.8	1.984	40	0.05	Significant
Effective Content Delivery	21.57	46.68						

Source: Field Survey 2025

The analysis in table 4.8 shows that the value for the t-transformation (t-trans.) is 6.8 while the value of the t-critical (t-crit) is 1.984. The value of the t-trans. is higher than the value of the t-crit. Therefore, there is significant relationship between OMT Lecturers' Graphic Design Skill and Effective Content Delivery in Universities in Rivers State.

Summary of Findings

The following were the findings in the study:

1. Office management and technology (OMT) lecturers Microsoft Access skills relates to effective content delivery at a high level and there is significant relationship between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Access skills and effective content delivery in Universities in Rivers State.
2. Office management and technology lecturers Microsoft Excel skills relates to effective content delivery at a high level. There is significant relationship between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Excel skills and effective content delivery in Universities in Rivers State.
3. Office management and technology lecturers graphic design skills relates to effective content delivery at a high level. There is significant relationship between OMT lecturers, graphic design skills and effective content delivery in Universities in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings in the study were discussed according to the objectives of the study;

Relationship between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Access skills and effective content delivery

From the analysis in table 4.1, $\Sigma x = 19.09$, $\Sigma y = 21.57$, the summation of x^2 and y^2 were thus 60.14 and 46.68, Σxy 41.9 and the r-calculated is 0.75. The value of the r-calculated (r-cal) indicates that there is a strong relationship between lecturers' Microsoft Access Skill and effective content delivery. It also shows that OMT lecturers' Microsoft Access skills relates with effective content delivery and there is significant relationship between OMT lecturers', Microsoft Access skills and effective content delivery in Rivers State Universities.

The findings is in agreement with view of Poole, Jackson and Randall (2015) who opined that knowledge of Microsoft Access enables one to know the records, fields, raw data, entire, characters and the basic building blocks that are contained in a file. In agreement with the view Poole, Jackson and Randall (2023), Cox and Lambert (2018) opined that knowledge of Microsoft Access enables one to display and modify tables data, design view and modify the structure of various documents as soft copy before the final print out.

Relationship between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Excel skills and effective content delivery

From the analysis in table 4.2, $\Sigma x = 14.94$, $\Sigma y = 21.57$, the summation of x^2 and y^2 are thus 54.4 and 46.68, Σxy 39.6 respectively and the r-calculated (r-cal) is 0.76. The value of the r-calculated shows that there is a strong relationship between lecturers' Microsoft Excel Skill and effective content delivery. it also shows that OMT lecturers Microsoft Excel skills relates with effective content delivery and there is significant relationship between OMT lecturers' Microsoft Excel skills and effective content delivery in Rivers State Universities.

This finding is in agreement with the view of Rentz (2018) who opined that the knowledge of Microsoft Excel can enable one to create and format work books in order to analyze data and make informed business decision. In agreement with the view of Rentz (2018), Entonyeaku (2019) opined that the new trends in the office are office information systems and these new trends in technological innovation place greater responsibilities on OMT lecturers to step up their game in content delivery.

Relationship between OMT Lecturers' Graphic Design Skill and Effective Content Delivery

The analysis in table 4.3 indicates that values of Σx and Σy are 18.23 and 21.57, Σx^2 and Σy^2 are 55.4 and 46.68 respectively, Σxy is 40.07 and the r-calculated value is 0.74. The r-calculated value indicates that there is a strong relationship between lecturers' Graphic Design Skill and effective content delivery. It also showed that OMT Lecturers' Graphic Design Skill relates with effective content delivery and there is significant relationship between OMT Lecturers' Graphic Design and effective content delivery in Rivers State Universities.

This finding is in agreement with view of Achoy in Nwana (2020) who opined that the knowledge of Graphic Design Skill by OMT Lecturers will enable OMT students to meet specific demands of their profession ranging from ability to capture digital images and necessary adjustment for use in publication work, ability to download, correct, manage and work with multi-image compositions.

In agreement with view of Achoy (2020) n Nwana (2020)opined that knowledge and use of Graphic Design by OMT Lecturers will enable students to have creativity, Photoshop, understand colour theory, understand layout/optimization and as well print designs.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it was concluded that the following operational skills: Microsoft Access, Microsoft Excel, Graphic design, Desktop publishing and Database Management relates to effective content delivery of OMT lecturers. Hence, the need for OMT lecturers to do more on the area of content delivery comes to light.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study and conclusion made, the following recommendations are made;

1. Microsoft Access skills should be adequately incorporated into the content delivery process of office management and technology.
2. Microsoft Excel skills of lecturers should be properly inculcated into the teaching and learning process in office management and technology programme in the Universities in Rivers State.
3. Office management and technology lecturers should improve more through an in-depth knowledge of Graphic design skills so as to enhance their content delivery.

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